

Evaluating Sustainable Aviation Fuels: A Comparative Analysis of Expert Groups

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Abstract

Employing sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs) stands as a pivotal stride in mitigating aviation's ecological footprint and realizing carbon neutrality. Yet, discerning the optimal SAF option demands a judicious evaluation encompassing economic feasibility, technical viability, and social acceptability. A multifaceted decision-making approach rooted in the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) underpins a comprehensive methodology for tackling this hurdle. This entailed engagement from three distinct expert cohorts: aviation operators, managers, and researchers. Their collective involvement ensured an exhaustive assessment of each component's significance in SAF selection. The AHP framework seamlessly orchestrated component prioritization based on their relative import, enabling decision-makers to reconcile divergent stakeholder objectives. The upshot of this appraisal is that it empowers policymakers and decision-makers to pinpoint the SAF variant aligning with their precise aims. The study's revelations underscore the paramount significance of evaluating environmental impact criteria, notably carbon emissions. Moreover, economic and technical viability emerged as pivotal factors in this selection juncture.

Keywords: Sustainable Aviation Fuels, Multi-Criteria Decision-Making, Analytic Hierarchy Process, Environmental Impact, Economic Feasibility.

I. Introduction

The aviation sector significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, particularly carbon dioxide, posing a substantial challenge to environmental mitigation in aviation (Perea-Moreno *et al.*, 2022). Global aviation emissions, as reported by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), comprised about 2.4% of the total CO₂ emissions in 2018 and are anticipated to escalate due to the expanding demand for air travel (Gössling and Humpe, 2020). Thus, mitigating aviation's environmental impact stands pivotal in attaining international climate objectives. One promising avenue to confront this challenge involves the advancement of sustainable aviation fuel (SAF), holding the potential to curtail aviation's carbon footprint while satiating escalating fuel requisites (Bergero *et al.*, 2023). SAF is derived from varied feedstocks like plant oils, municipal waste, and agricultural residues, substantially reducing carbon emissions by nearly 80% compared to traditional fossil fuels (Sharma *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, SAF seamlessly integrates with prevailing aviation infrastructure, encompassing aircraft, engines, and fueling systems, and can be blended with conventional fuels. Nevertheless, the development of SAF is influenced by multifaceted factors, encompassing economic, technical, and socio-cultural acceptability considerations. Effectively navigating these hurdles necessitates a collaborative approach involving industry stakeholders, policymakers, and the public. A primary obstacle in sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) advancement is production cost, notably surpassing traditional fossil fuels, primarily due to feedstock scarcity and costly conversion technologies (Tanzil *et al.*, 2021). The International Energy Agency (IEA) underscores this cost differential, indicating SAF production costs are presently two to six times higher than conventional jet fuel (Ng, Farooq and Yang, 2021). The absence of a definitive regulatory framework and carbon pricing mechanism further impedes SAF development and integration. Technical feasibility and social acceptability are pivotal considerations in SAF maturation (Lai, Karakaya and Björklund, 2022). Adhering to fuel specification requisites, encompassing energy density and combustion characteristics, is critical for technical feasibility, ensuring safety and efficacy. Simultaneously, modifying extant infrastructure for SAF storage and handling, necessitated by disparate freezing points compared to traditional jet fuel, poses an additional cost facet (Kramer *et al.*, 2022).

Addressing social acceptability becomes imperative, entailing public perception and acceptance of SAF (Anderson *et al.*, 2022). Health ramifications from SAF production and utilization, alongside community engagement, necessitate careful consideration (Xu *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, concerns regarding specific SAF feedstocks, like palm oil, and their adverse impacts on biodiversity and deforestation underscore the significance of responsible sourcing (Kurzawska, 2021). Furthermore, elevated particulate emissions from certain SAFs underline potential air quality and public health concerns.

Addressing these challenges necessitates multifaceted solutions, notably alternative feedstocks and innovative conversion technologies (Schmidt *et al.*, 2018). Establishing a transparent regulatory framework, implementing a carbon pricing mechanism, and fostering public awareness are pivotal components. The European Union's Renewable Energy Directive stands as a prime example, offering regulatory clarity and market signals promoting SAF development.

Sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) stands out as a promising remedy to mitigate aviation-related greenhouse gas emissions. However, the scarcity of raw materials and concerns about technical feasibility and social acceptability hamper its uptake. Thus, discerning preferences across various job categories and experience tiers regarding SAF is paramount for informed decision-making and policy sculpting within the aviation domain. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) presents a structured avenue, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of stakeholder SAF preferences (Saaty, 1990). By utilizing the "Saaty Scale" and AHP methodologies (Saaty, 2002), this study endeavors to unravel nuanced insights into diverse stakeholder orientations towards SAF, substantially contributing to strategic policy

frameworks and promoting SAF integration, thus advancing sustainability in aviation.

II. Methodology

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), a systematic, integrative approach by Saaty integrated for comprehensive evaluation (Omar and Utku, 2022), blends mathematical and psychological principles for complex decision-making. Pioneered by Thomas L. Saaty in the 1980s, AHP enables thorough evaluation and finds extensive use across various sectors (Saaty and Vargas, 2012).

An essential hierarchical model takes shape to delineate critical aspects of sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) and pinpoint the most pivotal constituent (Saaty, 2008). This model forms a structured tree-like representation, with the objective at the top, criteria, and sub-criteria in the middle, and alternatives at the base. Figure 1 illuminates the AHP decision-making process through a succinct flowchart.

Fig. 1 The steps of the AHP framework in SAF evaluation

A crucial step in this process is the creation of Pairwise Comparison Matrices (PCM), showcasing decision-makers preferences for specific option pairs. The Saaty scale (Table 1) ensures PCM elements are positive, transitive, and reciprocal, signifying consistency. Specialized aviation experts, well-versed in decision criteria, contribute through a thoughtfully designed questionnaire survey. Ongoing scrutiny of the consistency ratio (CR) is essential, rectifying any excess over 0.1 by reviewing judgments, scrutinizing inconsistencies, gathering more data, or seeking expert advice. This meticulous approach significantly enhances the understanding of critical SAF elements.

Table 1 Saaty scale (Saaty, 1977)

Mathematical representation	1	2,4,6,8	3	5	7	9
Meaning	Both aspects are equally important	Values between moderate and strong importance	One aspect is moderately more important than the other	One aspect is strongly more important than the other	One aspect is very strongly more important	One aspect is extremely more important than the other

Lastly, individual PCMs within each group amalgamate using the geometric mean aggregation method, culminating in a singular PCM epitomizing the group's preferences. The eigenvector method calculates model component weights. Utilizing the weighted sum method, prioritization unveils the paramount component in SAF selection. These meticulous AHP steps adeptly discern pivotal aspects and components steering SAF implementation within the contemporary aviation industry. Figure 2 delineates this hierarchical structure, offering a visual elucidation.

Fig. 2 The SAF Hierarchal structure

The SAF hierarchical approach provides a structured evaluation framework. Four levels assess environmental impact, economic and technical feasibility, and social acceptability. Next, Pairwise Comparison Matrices (PCMs) will assess model parameters and define critical model aspects.

III.Results and Discussions

The study utilized AHP, surveying 13 global aviation experts. Expertise-based segmentation provided varied industry perspectives. Job roles guided classification into aviation operators, managers, and researchers. The study quantified SAF evaluation challenges and aimed to enhance sustainability. Methodologically, participants were classified based on roles, and averages were derived using geometric mean. Weights and rankings for the SAF model's first-level elements were calculated for each group (see Table 2).

Table 2 AHP-comparison weights and priority ranking for experts' groups.

CRITERIA	AVIATION OPERATORS		MANAGEMENT		RESEARCHERS		AVERAGE	
	Weights	Rank	Weights	Rank	Weights	Rank	Weights	Rank
Environmental impact	45.23%	1	35.96%	1	39.90%	1	40.36%	1
Economic feasibility	18.38%	3	24.65%	2	28.58%	2	23.87%	2
Technical feasibility	20.97%	2	16.13%	4	15.87%	3	17.66%	4
Social acceptability	15.42%	4	23.25%	3	15.65%	4	18.11%	3

The table summarizes the criteria (environmental impact, economic feasibility, technical feasibility, social acceptability) for sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) as assessed by aviation operators. Environmental impact is the prime concern, emphasizing a growing awareness of environmental issues within the aviation industry. Conversely, social acceptability holds lesser weight, indicating lower priority for operators. Implementing these findings involves developing SAF with a reduced environmental impact while ensuring technical and economic feasibility. Effective communication and stakeholder engagement may address any social acceptability concerns. Management also emphasizes environmental impact, followed by economic feasibility, social acceptability, and technical feasibility. This balance suggests a conscious effort to integrate environmental concerns with economic and social considerations. Among researchers, environmental impact takes precedence, followed by economic and technical feasibility, with social acceptability noted as essential but less emphasized. These weightings reveal relationships between SAF production and the aviation system, highlighting the need to reduce environmental harm while considering practical limitations and aiming for public acceptance.

Fig 3. The hierarchal model comparison for all groups.

In order to gain a comprehensive overview of the survey results and discern key aspects from all experts' perspectives, a detailed model comparison is crucial. Figure 3 offers an extensive cross-group analysis, sorting aviation groups by participant experience levels. This figure facilitates the examination of diverse criteria across various perspectives, emphasizing pivotal factors. Across all groups, the environmental impact criterion consistently emerges as the most critical, with economic feasibility following, albeit with slight variations in the aviation operators' group. The overarching goal is to identify critical factors and their influence on the dynamic and stochastic aviation system.

IV. Conclusions

Sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs) represent a promising remedy for the aviation industry's environmental impact. However, choosing the optimal SAF demands a comprehensive economic feasibility assessment, technical viability, and social acceptance assessment. Employing a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) approach via the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), this study facilitated prioritization based on relative significance, enabling informed decisions that reconcile diverse and often conflicting stakeholder objectives. The results underscore the paramount importance of evaluating environmental impact criteria, particularly carbon emissions. Additionally, economic and technical feasibility are pivotal in the selection process. Policymakers and decision-makers can use these findings to pinpoint the most fitting SAF alternative aligned with their objectives. Overcoming challenges like production costs, feedstock limitations, high conversion technology expenses, regulatory gaps, and a lack of carbon pricing mechanisms is crucial for SAF development and adoption. Technical feasibility, ensuring compliance with fuel specifications for safety and performance, is equally vital. Fostering SAF demands a collaborative, multi-stakeholder effort involving industry, policymakers, and the public. The AHP method emerges as a valuable framework for prioritizing critical SAF selection factors, empowering decision-makers to harmonize diverse stakeholder objectives. SAF adoption stands pivotal in realizing global climate objectives, with this study's insights poised to guide policymakers and stakeholders in promoting sustainability within aviation.

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